

Impact of Foliar Boron Sprays on Seed Yield and Seed Quality of Sweet Pepper

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Introduction

Bell pepper (*Sweet pepper annum* L.) is an important spice-cum vegetable crop grown under various agro-climatic conditions. In Bangladesh popularity of sweet pepper is increasing day by day. Seed is the primary input, without which, the increase in production of any vegetable crop cannot be expected. Among inputs other than seed and fertilizers, application of micronutrients at the most appropriate concentration assumes special

ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted under pot culture and laboratory of Seed Technology Division, BARI, Gazipur during rabi season 2020-21 to find out the effect of foliar application of Boron on plant growth, seed yield, and quality of sweet pepper. The doses of Boron were 0ppm (control), 150ppm, 200ppm, 250ppm, 300ppm and 350ppm. Boron was applied as Boric acid (17.5% B) according to treatments spraying at the pre-flowering and flowering stage in the sweet pepper plant. Maximum number of fruits per plant (4.50), fresh weight of fruit (80.25g), seeds per fruit (161), number of seeds per plant (727.25), % germination (78.25%), root length (2.75cm) of seedling, shoot length (2.94cm) of seedling, vigor index (1.833) were found when plants were supposed to foliar spraying of Boron @250ppm. The tallest plant was found from 150ppm spray. Seed quality parameters were found better in the treatment of 200 ppm boron in the case of root length, shoot length and seedling length and vigor index of the seedling. Maximum fruit length (7.70cm) with an average fresh weight of fruit (75.25g) was obtained from 350ppm spray of Boron in sweet pepper.

Keywords: FOLIAR APPLICATION, PRE-FLOWERING, PPM, SEED QUALITY, SWEET PEPPER, VIGOR INDEX

significance for the production of higher seed yield with the better-quality seed of any vegetable crop. In recent years, the role of these micronutrients is gaining more importance, particularly in pepper to boost not only productivity but also to improve the seed quality. Boron is associated with the development of cell walls, cell differentiation, root elongation and shoot growth. It has been involved in carbohydrate synthesis, uptake of Ca^{2+} and absorption of NO_3^- . Boron also plays an important role in flowering and fruit formation (Nonnecke, 1989). The maturation of seeds is impaired in the absence of boron. Foliar feeding is a relatively new technique of feeding plants by applying liquid fertilizer directly to their leaves (Bernal *et al.*, 2007 and Baloch *et al.*, 2008). Studies revealed that the effect of foliar application of boron alone significantly enhanced the number of branches per plant and higher plant height in tomatoes (Rab and Haq, 2012), and higher seed yield and quality was obtained in soybean (Shruthi, 2013). The present study was, therefore, conducted to find out the effective dose of boron as a foliar spray to obtain higher seed yield and better seed quality of sweet pepper.

Materials and methods

The experiment was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) having 6 treatments and each treatment was replicated 5 times. The treatments were different doses of B *viz* T1 (control), T2 (150ppm), T3 (200ppm), T4 (250ppm), T5 (300ppm) and T6 (350ppm). The spray solution of boron was made of Boric acid diluted in distilled water. Seeds of BARI mistimorich-1 were used as sweet pepper variety in the experiment. Sweet pepper seedlings were grown in the seedbed and 30 days old seedlings were planted in the prepared soil of earthen pot (soil: FYM=5:1) @ one plant per pot. Plants were protected from mites by covering the planted area with a 16 meshed nylon net. Foliar feeding of Boron to the sweet pepper plants was done according to the treatments for two times *viz* pre-flowering and flowering stage

Method of data collection

Harvesting of fruits was started 95 DAT and continued up to final harvest based on maturity. Harvesting was done by hand picking of fruit. Data was recorded considering following parameters:

1. Plant height
2. Secondary branches per plant
3. Fruits per plant
4. Fresh weight of fruit (gram)
5. Fruit length (cm)
6. Seeds per fruit (number)
7. Seeds per plant (number)
8. Germination percentage: Seed germination was conducted in the Seed Technology laboratory using sand media at 25°C. 100 seeds with 4 replications were used for germination test. The first and final count was taken on 4th and 14th day of the test respectively. Germination percentage was worked out using the following formula:

Normal seedlings germinated

$$\text{Germination (\%)} = \frac{\text{Seeds kept for germination}}{\text{Seeds kept for germination}} \times 100$$

9. Seedling dry weight (g): For dry weight determination, the 10 normal seedlings were randomly selected on 14th day and dried in an oven at 71°C for 72 hrs using. Then cooled and weighed in an electronic weighing balance and expressed in gram.
10. Root length of seedling (cm)
11. Shoot length of seedling (cm)
12. Seedling length(cm)
13. Seedling Vigor Index: Vigor index was calculated on the basis of mean seedling dry weight by adopting the formula.

$$\text{Vigor index} = \text{Germination (\%)} \times \text{Seedling dry weight (g)}$$

Statistical Analysis

All data were analyzed by using Statistic software (version 10.0) and a comparison of treatment means was done by using LSD test at 5 % level of significance.

Results and Discussion

The result of the present investigation related to plant growth and yield are presented in Table 1.

Plant Height

Foliar application of Boron elicited significant variation for plant height at the final harvest. The tallest plants were obtained from 150ppm Boron spray (68.50cm). Statistically similar plant height was found in the case of 250, 300, 350ppm Boron Spray. Similarly, Shnain *et al.* (2014) found increased plant height in pepper by foliar spray of 75 ppm boron, Rajana *et al.* (2018) found higher plant height (64.16cm) in Greengram by foliar spray of 0.2% of boron at 20 and 35 DAS, Haleema *et al.* (2018) obtained an increase in plant height due to the application of boron (0.25%) in tomato, higher plant height in french bean was also recorded by 2.5ppm boron treatment over control (Padma *et al.*,1989).

Secondary branches per plant

Secondary branches per plant did not show significant variation from each other for the treatments. Significant variation was found in case of number of fruit per plant. Average 4.5 fruits per plant were collected from 250ppm spray of Boron that was statistically similar to 200ppm Boron spray. Minimum fruiting was found in control and 150ppm spray. Supporting this result, Bora and Hazarika (1997) found increased number of siliqua in toria through the application of boron as foliar spray.

Fresh weight of fruit

A significant difference was found for the treatments in case of fresh weight of fruit. Maximum 80.50g fruit was found in treatment of 250ppm Boron that was statistically similar to 350ppm Boron spray.

Fruit length

A significant variation was found also for fruit length. Maximum fruit length (7.70cm) was found in 350ppm Boron spray that was statistically similar to 350ppm Boron spray. Tiwari and Yadava (1990) reported that foliar application of boron (1ppm) at 45 days old plants of Siratro recorded highest number of pods (65.00), length of pods (8.69 cm).

Number of seeds per fruit

The number of seeds per fruit was significantly varied for the treatments where maximum 161 seeds per fruit were found from treatment 250ppm spray and minimum was found in control. Similarly, Kumar and Malabasari (2011) recorded significantly higher number of seeds per fruit (221.20) through foliar spray of borax (0.5%) in bell pepper and higher number of seeds per fruit in chili (83.4) from (0.1%) foliar spray of borax at flowering stage was also recorded by Natesh *et al.* (2005)

Table 1. Effect Boron concentration on plant growth and yield related parameters of sweet pepper

Boron Conc. (ppm)	Plant height (cm)	Secondary branches/ plant (nos.)	Fruit/plant (nos.)	Fresh weight of fruit(g)	Fruit length(cm)	Seeds/fruit (nos.)
0	54.75 bc	4.25 a	2.75 c	63.50 b	6.20 bc	73.50 e
150	68.50 a	4.50 a	2.75 c	39.25 c	6.45 bc	128.25 b
200	58.50 b	4.50 a	3.75 ab	45.00 c	5.90 c	101.50 d
250	52.75 c	4.00 a	4.50 a	80.25 a	6.53 b	161.25 a
300	52.25 c	4.00 a	3.25 bc	37.50 c	4.25 d	114.25 c
350	55.50 bc	4.50 a	3.00 bc	75.25 a	7.70 a	104.25 d
CV%	5.34	12.94	8.97	8.79	6.07	3.26

Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Seeds per plant

Seed yield data showed significant variation for the treatments. Maximum seeds per plant (727.25) was obtained when plants sprayed with 250 ppm Boron that was gradually reduced with increase in concentration of Boron spray. Minimum seeds per plant was found in control that was gradually increased with Boron spray upto 250ppm. Foliar spray of borax (0.1%) at flowering stage gave higher number of seeds per plant (83.4) in chilli

(*Sweet pepper annuum* L.) was recorded by Natesh *et al.* (2005) and significantly higher number of seeds (221.20) from foliar spray of borax (0.5%) was recorded by Kumar and Malabasari (2011).

Figure 1. Seed yield per plant as affected by concentration of Boron spray.

The influence of the foliar application of Boron in sweet pepper was also found significant for the treatments in the case of seed quality parameters.

Table 2. Effect on seed quality parameters

Boron Conc. (ppm)	Germination %	Root length (cm)	Shoot length (cm)	Seedling length (cm)	Dry weight of 10 seedlings (g)	Seedling Vigor Index
0	63.00 b	2.135 b	2.355 c	4.490 c	0.021 ab	1.265 bc
150	48.50 c	2.275 ab	2.380 c	4.655 bc	0.022 ab	1.031cd
200	67.50 b	2.665 ab	2.810 ab	5.475 a	0.023 a	1.643 ab
250	78.75 a	2.750 a	2.940 a	5.475 a	0.024 a	1.833 a
300	38.25 d	2.330 ab	2.615 bc	4.945 abc	0.017 b	0.665 d
350	65.75 b	2.602 ab	2.795 ab	5.397 ab	0.021 ab	1.527 ab
CV (%)	9.90	6.34	7.04	9.80	5.09	20.85

Means followed by the same letter in each column are not significantly different at 5% level.

Germination percentage

Maximum 78% seed germination was found in treatment 250ppm spray of Boron and minimum germination was 38% found in treatment 300ppm. Verma *et al.* (2004) also found a foliar spray of borax 0.5% showing a positive effect on percent seed germination (85.66) in sweet pepper and Kumari (2012) found (95%) germination in tomatoes from foliar application of boron.

Seedling length

Maximum root length was found (2.75cm) in 250ppm treatment that was statistically similar to other treatments except for the control. A significant variation was obtained in shoot length. Maximum shoot length was found (2.94cm) in 250ppm treatment that was statistically similar to 200ppm and 350ppm treatment. Maximum seedling length (5.475cm) was found in treatment 200ppm and 250ppm Boron that was statistically similar to 300ppm and 350ppm treatment.

Dry weight of seedlings

Statistically, a similar result was found in case of the dry weight of seedlings within the treatments.

Seedling Vigor index

The concentration of Boron spray largely affects the vigor index of the seedling. Seedling vigor index was observed higher in treatment 250ppm of Boron that was statistically similar to treatment 200ppm and 350ppm of Boron. Similarly, Kumar and Malabasari (2011) found a higher seedling vigor index (1000.4) from the foliar spray of borax (0.5%) in bell pepper.

Conclusion

Considering the result of the above study, the conclusion may be drawn as the plant growth and seed quality parameters *viz* the number of fruits per plant, fresh weight of fruit, number of seed per fruit, seed yield per plant, germination, root length, shoot length of seedlings and vigor index were found maximum from the foliar spraying of Boron @ 250ppm in sweet pepper. The result now provides evidence to an increase in seed yield with better seed quality could be obtained through foliar application of Boron @ 250ppm in sweet pepper.

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